

Varying Valency of Platinum with respect to Mercaptanic Radicles. Part VI.

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The action of bases on the complex compounds derived from chloroplatinic acid and thio-compounds (mercaptans, sulphides) has not only furnished valuable informations regarding the constitution of the complex compounds but has helped us in proving that the valency of platinum is variable (Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 872; Rây, *ibid.*, 1922, 121, 1289; Rây, *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 133; Rây and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 178; Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 155; Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, *ibid.*, 1926, 4, 358).

The present work was undertaken with a view to throw further light on the interesting question of the variability of the valency of platinum. In this paper are described the results obtained by the action of ammonia and amine bases on the complex compound, $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{S}_2$, derived from chloroplatinic acid and triethylene trisulphide (Rây, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 1288).

The results indicate that most of the complex compounds can be represented on the Werner model, whereas others are to be regarded as molecular compounds. Indirectly the constitution of the complex compound appears to be

as will be evident from the following considerations:—

By the action of ammonia, $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{S}_2$ is converted into the well-known compound $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$ (Carlgreen and Cleve, *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 1, 67). This may be most conveniently represented on the Werner model as

That the chlorine atoms in the above are ionisable has been proved by conductivity measurement (*vide* experimental). A

compound of the same composition but not identical in physical properties has been obtained from ammonia and $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ by Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây, (this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 156)

Benzylamine is found to give with $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot (\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$ a compound having the composition $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 4 \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$ which may be expressed by the Werner model, thus—

Any direct proof as to the ionisability or non-ionisability of chlorine cannot be adduced as no ionising solvent could be found. This compound has previously been obtained from $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot 2 \text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and benzylamine by Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 360).

By the action of ethylenediamine on $\text{PtCl}_4 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$, the following three compounds have been isolated:—

Of these (i) is a well-known compound of the Werner type and may be represented in the following way (cf. Jorgensen, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1899, (2), 39, 4, 1949).

The ionisability of chlorine in the above has been shown by precipitation with silver nitrate.

The compound $\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 3\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$ is a molecular compound of $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 3 \text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$. Evidently the group (C_2H_5) is eliminated during the reaction giving rise to 1:4-dithian, which then polymerises to triethylene trisulphide (Rây and Bose-Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 73).

The compound $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{S}_2$ may be expressed either as a molecular compound of the type $\text{AgCl} \cdot \text{NH}$ or on the Werner type, thus:

Pyridine acting on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$ produces three compounds, namely.

The compound (i) at the very first sight seems to be a molecular compound of $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$, but the substance could not be broken up into the component molecules owing to its insolubility in all common solvents.

Compound (ii) may be constituted as follows (*cf.* Kurnakow, *Zeit. anorg. Chem.*, 17, 214)

That the two chlorine atoms are ionisable has been proved by (i) the action of silver nitrate, and by (ii) conductivity measurements (*vide* experimental). The same compound has been obtained previously from $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ and pyridine by Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây (*loc. cit.*).

Compound (iii) may be represented on the Werner model thus (Jorgensen, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1886, [2], 33, 504).

This compound is also obtained when $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ is heated to 140° . During the change 2 molecules of pyridine are eliminated from the nucleus and 2 chlorine atoms enter the complex. The transformation may be shown thus:—

The same compound has been previously obtained by the interaction of pyridine and $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ by Rây, Guha and Bose-Rây (*loc. cit.*).

Dimethylaniline is found to give $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$, with $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$. This compound cannot be expressed as a complex compound of the Werner type, but may be regarded as a

simple molecular compound of $PtCl_3$ and $C_5H_9N(CH_3)_3$ of the type of $AgCl.NH_3$.

By the action of piperidine on $PtCl_3.(C_5H_9)_3S_3$, $PtCl_3.3C_5H_{11}N$ has been isolated. Probably it has the constitution :—

but evidence in favour of the above constitution is not available as the compound is insoluble in all the ionising solvents.

Interaction of tripropylamine and $PtCl_3.(C_3H_7)_3S_3$ leads to $PtCl_3.(C_3H_7)_2S_3$, the "thio" part being not replaced by the base. Only one atom of chlorine and the radicle (C_3H_7) are removed during the reaction. The compound may be regarded as a molecular one of the type of $AgCl.NH_3$ or may be constituted according to Werner, thus :—

Diethylamine acting on $PtCl_3.(C_2H_5)_3S_3$ produces

The former is a compound of the Werner type and may be represented thus—

One molecule of the base of the above compound is replaced by one molecule of acetone when it is crystallised from that solvent giving rise to the compound (ii), which may consequently be represented as

By the action of phenylenediamine on $PtCl_3.(C_6H_5)_3S_3$, the compound $Pt_2Cl_3.4C_6H_4(NH_2)_2$ has been isolated.

In all the above cases it will be noticed that the original compound $PtCl_3.(C_3H_7)_3S_3$ is reduced by the action of the base, in most cases one atom of chlorine being eliminated. Direct proof in support of the view that one of the three chlorine atoms in the molecule is

more reactive in comparison with the other two could not be adduced as the compound $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$ is insoluble in most organic or ionising media. The reactions with bases, however, indirectly support the assumption. Representing the compound by formula (I) the mechanism of reaction in most cases can be represented by the following scheme:—

Compounds of the type (III) are found in (i) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}$, and (ii) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_3$. Type (IV) is represented by $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 3 \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}$, whereas (i) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4 \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$; (ii) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4 \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}$. (iii) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4 \text{NH}_3$ and (iv) $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2 \text{C}_2\text{H}_5(\text{NH}_2)_2$ are of the type (V).

The results obtained moreover show that in most cases the behaviour of $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$ towards bases is very similar to that of $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{S}$ or $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{PhCH}_2)_2\text{S}$ (Roy Chowdhury, *private communication*) and that the parent substance is to be regarded as having the structure (I).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Action of Ammonia on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$.

The compound was suspended in water and ammonia was passed in for about one hour. The solid gradually went into solution and a white solid separated out which was found to be dithian. The liquid was filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness in a vacuum desiccator. The solid product was redissolved in a small quantity of water and precipitated by a little alcohol. This was filtered and found to be impure and was therefore rejected. To the filtrate a further quantity of alcohol was added when a brownish precipitate was obtained which was well washed with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator.

The substance is very hygroscopic and did not melt when heated up to 200°. (Found: Pt, 58·61; Cl, 21·71; N, 16·98; S, absent. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$ requires Pt, 58·88; Cl, 21·26; N, 16·76 per cent.)

Conductivity Measurement of $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$.

0·2108 gm. of the substance in 100 c.c. of water; hence concentration = M/159. Cell constant = 0·095.

Strength of the soln. Observed resistance. Molecular conductivity.

M/159	56	=270 (approx).
M/1590	488	=315 (approx).

Thus molecular conductivity at about 1600 litres dilution (which may be taken to approach infinite dilution) = 315, a value which is intermediate between the values for a ternary and a quaternary electrolyte.

Action of AgNO_3 on $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$.

The substance was dissolved in water and precipitated by AgNO_3 in the cold. HNO_3 was not added as it might break up the complex. The result obtained, though low, is sufficiently convincing to indicate that both the chlorine atoms are ionisable. (Found: Cl, 19·42. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{NH}_3$ requires Cl, 21·26 (when both the chlorine atoms are ionisable) or Cl, 10·68 per cent. (when one chlorine atom is ionisable).)

Action of Benzylamine.

The compound was just covered with benzylamine and heated on a water-bath for about half an hour. On cooling a semi-solid mass was obtained. It was several times washed with ether and boiling alcohol to remove dithian, benzylamine, etc., and then with little water followed by alcohol. The solid mass was then crystallised from boiling chloroform as fine silky, white crystals, m.p. 195°. (Found: Pt, 28·2; Cl, 10·9; N, 8·21. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$ requires Pt, 28·3; Cl, 10·2; N, 8·07 per cent.)

Action of Ethylenediamine.

The compound was just covered with an aqueous solution of ethylenediamine (about 1 per cent.) and the product was heated on a water-bath for 6-7 hours. It was then filtered and the filtrate,

on slow evaporation in a vacuum desiccator, yielded a crop of white crystalline substance, which was washed with a little water and alcohol and dried. It had no m.p. (Found: Pt, 41.10; Cl, 21.15; N, 9.77; S, 10.15. $\text{Pt}_2\text{Cl}_6, 3\text{C}_2\text{H}_5(\text{NH}_2)_2, (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$ requires Pt, 40.50; Cl, 22.10; N, 8.72; S, 10.15 per cent.).

The insoluble yellow portion was washed with hot water, alcohol, benzene and ether, and dried. (Found: Pt, 50.42; Cl, 17.96; S, 17.42. $\text{PtCl}_2, (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$ requires Pt, 50.52; Cl, 18.39; S, 16.59 per cent.).

The compound was treated with an excess of ethylenediamine solution in water (1:5) and heated on a water-bath for about forty-five minutes. Dithian separated out during the reaction and was deposited on the colder part of the reacting vessel. This was then filtered off and the filtrate kept in a vacuum desiccator. The insoluble precipitate was found to be dithian. The mother-liquor on spontaneous evaporation yielded a crop of white crystals which were collected, washed with minimum quantity of water and alcohol and dried. The substance did not melt when heated up to 220°. (Found: Pt, 50.14; Cl, 18.30; N, 14.50. $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5(\text{NH}_2)_2$ requires Pt, 50.51; Cl, 18.39; N, 14.50 per cent.).

This compound is mainly obtained even if a large excess of 4 per cent. solution of ethylenediamine is used.

Action of Silver Nitrate on $\text{PtCl}_2, 2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5(\text{NH}_2)_2$.

The substance was dissolved in water, as in the previous case without using nitric acid and treated with AgNO_3 . The result obtained is low as before. (Found: Cl, 17.60. Calc. Cl, 18.39 (when both the chlorine atoms are ionisable).

Action of Pyridine on $\text{PtCl}_2, (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{S}_2$.

The compound was treated with an excess of pyridine and heated on a water-bath for about eight hours. The liquid was then filtered off and the solid residue washed with hot pyridine two or three times. The filtrates, on evaporation, yielded transparent white crystals which were washed with chloroform to remove dithian. The substance was recrystallised from pyridine, washed with chloroform and dried. It turned yellow above 140° but did not melt. (Found: Pt, 33.1; Cl, 11.7; N, 8.84. $\text{PtCl}_2, 4\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}$ requires Pt, 33.50; Cl, 12.19; N, 9.62 per cent.).

*Ionisability of PtCl₂.4C₅H₅N.**(a) Conductivity Method.—*

Concentration of the solution, M/1221 ;

Resistance found=420 ; Cell constant = .095

Hence, Molecular conductivity at 1221 litres dilution=270, *i.e.*, the substance is a ternary electrolyte.

(b) Precipitation Method.—

The substance was dissolved in water as in previous cases without using nitric acid. The result was low. (Found : Cl, 11.24. Calc. Cl, 12.19 per cent.).

The portion insoluble in pyridine was several times extracted with hot chloroform. The chloroform extract on evaporation gave shining yellow crystals which were filtered and dried. These had no m. p. (Found : Pt, 46.85, 46.3; Cl, 17.01; N, 6.50. PtCl₂.2C₅H₅N requires Pt, 46.00; Cl, 16.75; N, 6.60 per cent.).

The portion insoluble in chloroform was then washed several times successively with warm water, alcohol, chloroform, benzene and alcohol, and dried. No m.p. (Found : Pt, 40.52; Cl, 26.1; N, 5.85; C, 24.85; H, 2.18. Pt₂Cl₇. 4C₅H₅N requires Pt, 40.8; Cl, 26.19; N, 5.86; C, 25.09; H, 2.09 per cent.).

Action of Dimethylaniline.

The compound was treated with an excess of dimethylaniline and heated on a water-bath for about an hour. The mass became greenish blue. It was filtered and the solid residue washed several times with alcohol, water, alcohol and benzene and dried. The product in the filtrate could not be isolated in a pure condition. (Found : Pt, 49.93; Cl, 18.01; N, 8.01. PtCl₂. C₅H₅N (CH₃)₂ requires Pt, 50.40; Cl, 18.35; N, 8.61 per cent.).

Action of Piperidine.

The compound was digested with an excess of piperidine on a water-bath for half an hour. A semi-solid mass was obtained which, on treatment with excess of ether, gave a crystalline compound. This was filtered and washed thoroughly with ether and alcohol and dried in a desiccator. The substance did not melt when heated up to 200°. (Found : Pt, 37.3; Cl, 13.51; N, 8.39. PtCl₂. 8C₅H₁₁N requires Pt, 37.4; Cl, 13.6; N, 8.06 per cent.).

Action of Tripropylamine.

The compound was digested with excess of tripropylamine on a water-bath for twelve hours. A yellowish green pasty mass was obtained. This was filtered, washed with water, alcohol, ether, benzene and chloroform, and the resulting yellow mass dried. (Found: Pt, 50.57; Cl, 18.81; S, 16.84. $\text{PtCl}_2(\text{C}_3\text{H}_7)_3\text{S}_2$ requires Pt, 50.52; Cl, 18.89; S, 16.59 per cent.).

Action of Diethylamine.

The compound was refluxed with an excess of diethylamine on a water-bath for three hours. It was then filtered and the solid residue washed several times with boiling alcohol, benzene and ether. The residue was then digested with chloroform and the chloroform solution on spontaneous evaporation yielded white crystals which were dried in a desiccator. (Found: Pt, 46.95; Cl, 17.63. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}$ requires Pt, 47.53; Cl, 17.14 per cent.).

When the above substance is recrystallised from hot acetone, a shining yellow crystalline substance containing acetone is obtained. (Found: Pt, 50.18; Cl, 18.04; C, 21.52; H, 5.02%. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot (\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH} \cdot (\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CO}$ requires Pt, 49.12; Cl, 17.88; C, 21.16; H, 4.85 per cent.).

Action of p-Phenylenediamine.

The compound was treated with an aqueous solution of *p*-phenylene diamine hydrochloride and heated on a water-bath. The violet insoluble portion was filtered, washed several times with water and alcohol and dried. The product in the filtrate could not be isolated in a pure state. (Found: Pt, 42.43; Cl, 11.04. $\text{PtCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2$ requires Pt, 42.08; Cl, 11.47 per cent.).

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* Percentage of hydrogen came rather high since the substance was mixed with copper oxide before combustion.

